

HISTORY

GENOCIDE CARRIED OUT IN WESTERN AZERBAIJAN IN 1918-1920

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Abstract

Four times in the 20th century (1905-1906, 1918-1920, 1948-1953, 1988-1991) Azerbaijanis were deported from the territory of present-day Armenia - their historical-ethnic land - with massacres. Armenians fighting for "Turkless Armenia" and their ideologues, as well as their patrons from near and far abroad, completed the ethnic cleansing operation in the 90s of the 20th century. The last settlement of Azerbaijanis in Armenia - the village of Nuvedi was subjected to genocide by the Armenians and the indigenous inhabitants of the village - Azerbaijanis - were deported from their historical and ethnic lands. Thus, not a single Azerbaijani remained in Western Azerbaijan, which is now called Armenia. This article talks about the genocides carried out by Armenians against the Azerbaijani people in Western Azerbaijan in 1918-1920. Valuable documents proving these genocides are today in the documents of the Extraordinary Investigation Commission preserved in the National Archives of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the "General Staff Military History and Strategic Studies Archive", the "Başbakanlık Ottoman Archive" of the Republic of Turkey and the "Political Archive of the German Ministry of Foreign Affairs" in Berlin, Germany "(Politischen Archiv den Auswärtigen) are preserved in the funds of the First World War and the War of Independence. The actual materials in those archival documents prove that from 1917 to 1920, Armenians mercilessly killed tens of thousands of peaceful, unarmed Turkish-Muslim population in Zangazur district of Azerbaijan due to their ethnicity. Historical facts are shown in the article referring to these sources.

Keywords: Western Azerbaijan, Yerevan, Zangazur, genocide, Turkish-Muslim, Armenians.

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Introduction

At the beginning of the 20th century, Armenians purposefully implemented the policy of genocide in the territory of Azerbaijan. Taking advantage of the political situation after the February revolution and the October coup in 1917, the Armenians colluded with the Bolsheviks and committed genocide against the Turkish-Muslim population. The main goal was to weaken the social base of "Musavat", which won the elections to the Baku Soviet. The Armenian-Bolshevik forces led by S. Shaumyan started from Baku and from March 31 continued in Shamakhi, Lankaran, Zangezur, Iravan, as well as in Urmiya, Khoy and Maku. This is not the first murder committed by Armenians against the local population. Armenians tried to implement their plans by abusing the disruption of historical and political stability. Thus, trying to benefit from the revolution that took place in Tsarist Russia in 1905-1907, Armenians committed genocide against the Turkish-Muslim population. Unthinkable crimes were committed against the peaceful, innocent population during these events, which are recorded in history as the Armenian-Muslim conflict. There is enough information about this in historical sources. In the works "Bloody Years" by Mammad Said Ordubadi and "Armenian-Muslim conflict in 1905-1906" by Mir Mohsen Nawab, important facts related to the atrocities committed against Azerbaijanis in 1905-1906 were found. In the 1905-1906 editions of the "Kaspi" newspaper printed in Baku in Russian, as well as in the book "Armenian-Turkish

clashes in the Caucasus (1905-1906)" by A. Don, published in Armenian in 1907, with the events that took place during that period related information can be found [1, 36]. However, Azerbaijanis did not learn from this, even after these events, they wrote works promoting humanism and coexistence. However, such works by Armenians do not exist.

At that time, they covered up this genocide, which was organized by the Dashnak military forces, in a different way. Thus, the Armenian Bolsheviks, led by Stepan Shaumyan, tried to paint it as a civil war and thereby cover up the real historical truth. The ugly, criminal acts of Armenians who committed genocide in Azerbaijan are known from archival materials and witness statements. However, despite this, after the establishment of the Soviet government in Azerbaijan, this issue was not objectively investigated in a scientific direction, and in historiography, the genocide committed against the Azerbaijani people was characterized as "civil war", "Musavat massacre", and "March Uprising". However, after the fall of the USSR, the opportunity to objectively investigate the historical truths was obtained. It was possible to express and analyze historical documents and sources as they are. This is a direct blow to the plans of the Armenians and their patrons, who are trying to falsify and hide their actions.

Genocide in Zangezur

In 1918-1920, Zangezur district was one of the territories of Azerbaijan that suffered the genocide of Armenians. Armenian gangs led by Andranik and Nijde attacked the territories of Azerbaijan, threatened the

population, and called for submission to the Armenian government. Those who did not submit to the Armenian government had to leave the city or become victims of Andranik's brutal crimes. It should be noted that in the 19th century, as a result of the Russo-Qajar and Russo-Turkish wars, Armenians from both Ottoman and Qajar empires and other regions of Tsarist Russia were moved to this area with the agreements concluded between the parties. As a result of the resettlement, the Armenians who settled in the historical lands of Azerbaijan carried out a policy of ethnic cleansing against the local population. It is no coincidence that the Armenian population living here played an active role in the genocide carried out in the 20th century. When Andranik's and others' gangs attacked, the Armenians living in these areas also supported the implementation of the genocide, since they were resettled here in the 19th century, they knew the region better, which allowed them to help the attacking gangs and strike from within against the Azerbaijanis who were trying to defend themselves.

On July 15, 1918, the government of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic established an Extraordinary Commission of Inquiry to investigate the genocide against Azerbaijanis in 1918 [13, 27]. The massacres that took place through this institution were investigated, witness statements and information obtained from those involved in the investigation once again confirm that the Armenian-Bolshevik forces committed genocide on purpose. Two of the 36 volumes of investigative materials examined by this institution refer to the events that took place in Zangezur. It is known from the documents of the Extraordinary Investigation Commission that 115 villages of Zangezur district were destroyed by Armenians. The names of those villages are mentioned in these documents. [6 p. 127]. 3257 men, 2276 women, 2196 children were killed from 115 villages. In addition, it should be noted that 10,068 Azerbaijanis were killed by Armenians and maimed as a result of serious injuries before the report of the Extraordinary Investigation Commission was prepared. The chaotic and unstable situation during the events of the genocide did not allow identifying all of the victims of Armenian atrocities [3, 166].

The events that took place in Zangezur accident are proof of Armenian atrocities. Armenians killed the population mercilessly. This can be seen from the facts and examples known from the investigation. Children's corpses found on the streets of Sheki village, divided into two parts, nursing babies who were bayoneted in Irmishli village, families burned alive along with their houses, people whose hands, feet, and various organs were cut off and put in a terrible condition show the scale and horror of the murders committed by Armenians [9, 47]. With this, they tried to create fear among the population and drive the survivors out of their places once and for all with such "examples". Armenians did not ignore the religion and customs of the population and did not hesitate to damage the holy places. Thus, in the village of Vagudu of Zangezur district, more than 400 people, who assumed that the Armenians would not touch the mosque, hid there and tried to

protect themselves in the mosque. However, the Armenians threw a bomb into the mosque, set it on fire and burned it together with the people inside it [6, 128]. It should be noted that the damage done to holy places and historical monuments does not end there. The genocides committed by Armenians against the people of Azerbaijan and the policy of ethnic cleansing do not consist only of the events that took place in 1918-20. From the end of the 20th century, starting from the 80s, they began to occupy the territories of Azerbaijan. As a result, they have damaged the monuments and material-cultural examples here. It is enough to show that animals were kept in mosques.

The attacks, which started in 1918, intensified in November 1919. Armenians organized more extensive attacks and carried out heavy operations in the villages of Zangezur such as Okchu, Atgiz, and Shabadan. Since 1920, it was the Republic of Ararat that organized the intensification of these massacres [4]. The main purpose of this was to cleanse Zangezur of Azerbaijanis and completely armenize it, and after capturing Zangezur, it was permanently captured by the main states that participated in the Paris peace conference and legitimized it. It is no coincidence that the official armed forces of Ararat state participated in the process of ethnic cleansing.

From January 1920, letters were sent to the Parliament of Azerbaijan and political circles about the deterioration of the situation in Zangezur, mass massacres committed by Armenians, and they asked for help to prevent Armenian atrocities. Among such telegrams addressed to the government of Azerbaijan, it is possible to mention the ones sent by Jalil Sultanov, a member of the Azerbaijani parliament who visited Zangezur, and Huseyn Akhundzade, a teacher from Jabrayil. From the telegrams sent on January 21 and 23, 1920, it is once again clear that the Armenians were mercilessly oppressing the Azerbaijani people and trying to seize these territories by committing genocide against the population. As stated in the telegram sent by Jalil Sultanov on January 23, 1920, the goal of the Armenians was to completely capture the territories of Karabakh, Nakhchivan, Irvan, and Zangezur, to remove the local population from here and to armenize them: completely destroyed. The number of regular Armenian army that participated in the battle reaches ten thousand. According to the information we received, an attack on Jabrayil district will be launched tomorrow from the Zangezur side. The goal of the Armenians is to completely cut off the connection with Nakhchivan, thus solving the issue of both Karabakh and Nakhchivan once and for all. The time has come to put an end to the protests on paper, to reveal to the world the treacherous Armenians who led to the destruction of the over two hundred thousand Zangezur Muslim population. Please take immediate action so that at least Shusha and Gabriel can be saved. Every minute is precious. Being late is equal to crime and treason in front of the people and the country" [6, 130].

It should be noted that what was written in the book "Garagin Nizhde i ego ucheniya («Гарагин Нижде и его учения») published in Armenia in 2004 about the genocide in Zangezur is proof of the actions

committed by Armenians. It is written here that more Azerbaijanis were killed, and that 200 villages inhabited by Turks and Tatars were "returned" to Armenians. This should be considered as an acknowledgment of the actions committed by Armenians [16, 8]

Genocide in Iravan

With the collapse of empires at the end of the First World War, peoples had the opportunity to determine their own destiny. As a result, with the collapse of Tsarist Russia, the peoples of the Caucasus managed to declare their independence. The Republic of Azerbaijan, Armenia (Ararat) and Georgia were formed in the South Caucasus. There were problems in determining the borders of the states. Thus, Armenians trying to realize the dream of "Great Armenia" wanted to set the borders according to the borders of this desired "state". According to the unfounded claims of Armenians, the Armenian state should have included the territories of the Ottoman Empire, Azerbaijan and Georgia. They tried to realize these plans in the following years [10, 49]. Territorial disputes with Azerbaijan and Georgia are also the result of this policy of the Armenians, who are trying to appropriate the ancient and eternal lands of the peoples in order to build the "Great Armenia", which never existed and is only a dream. In order to realize their plans, the Armenians, who tried to seize foreign lands, and for this purpose, tried to expel the local, aboriginal population from their homeland by committing murders and exiles, although they could not build the "Great Armenia" of their dreams, they managed to create the currently existing Republic of Armenia.

On May 29, 1918, in order to end the massacres committed by the Armenians against Azerbaijan, the groundless territorial claims, the government of Azerbaijan was forced to give its historical lands, Iravan, to the Armenians as the capital. The main condition for the concession of Yerevan to the Armenians was that the Armenians renounced their claims to other territories. One of the factors that created conditions for this was the transfer of Gyumri (Alexandropol) territories, which the Armenians envisioned as the capital, to the control of the Ottomans [8, 136]. According to the information stored in the Russian archives, it is clear that the Provisional government, which was established after the February revolution of 1917, also used Armenians for its own purposes. For this purpose, he adopted the concept of "Turkey Armenia" [15, 356-357]. To weaken and defeat the Ottomans, the Russian, British and other forces used the Armenians living here, giving them promises and making concessions to create a state. The goal was to strengthen in these areas and to use the Armenians as a political tool for this. The fact that both the newly formed government, the successor of Tsarist Russia, and Soviet Russia drew Armenians to their side served this purpose. They tried to create a state for them by applying the concept of "Turkey-Armenia". However, as is known from history, the plan to create a state for Armenians was transferred to the Caucasus because the Ottoman state later liberated those territories. With this, the Armenian state was estab-

lished in the historical lands of Azerbaijan in the territory of the South Caucasus - in the lands of Western Azerbaijan [12, 249]

Iravan was one of the territories of Azerbaijan where Armenians committed genocide. Back in November 1917, after the October coup in Russia, Armenians who seized the weapons of the Russian troops retreating from Eastern Anatolia and the Caucasus front committed genocides against Turks and Azerbaijanis. Thus, on December 5, 1917, an agreement was signed in Erzincan between the South Caucasian Commissariat and the Ottoman government. After that, the Armenians, who took advantage of the retreat of the Russian troops from Eastern Anatolia, seized the weapons and started slaughtering the Turkish-Muslim population [14, 21]. In this regard, information is also provided in the documents kept in the political archive of the German Ministry of Foreign Affairs. At that time, the German representative in the South Caucasus, Bernstroff, sent to the German Ministry of Foreign Affairs on February 27, 1918, it was written: "Atrocities committed by Armenian volunteer groups in Erzincan should be considered very important. The population in the villages was completely destroyed" [11, 41].

From the beginning of 1918, Armenian armed groups started to commit mass massacres against Azerbaijanis in Iravan province. Until March 1918, Armenian armed groups destroyed 198 villages, including 32 villages in Iravan District, 84 in Echmiadzin District, 7 in Yeni-Beyazid District, and 75 in Surmali District of Iravan Governorate. In those districts, approximately 135,000 Azerbaijanis were subjected to genocide [6, 133].

Until September 1919, except for some village of Zangibasar, all the villages of Iravan district and also of Vedibasar were destroyed, their inhabitants were mercilessly killed, and the survivors were removed from their native lands. In 1920, the "Azerbaijan" newspaper published information about this in April: "There are no more Muslims left in Goycha district. Currently, 84 Muslim villages have been destroyed in Yeni Beyazid district, 22 of them were destroyed in April alone. Tashkent, Goshabulaq, Sariyagub, Bash Shorja, Ashagi Shorja, Sogangulu-Agali, Agkilsa, Zoda, Gulu, Agali, B. Garagoyunlu, K. Garagoyunlu, Zarzibil, Adli, Inakdag, Garaiman, Kaseman, Bashkend, Bala Marza, Shishgaya, Bash The population of Haji and Garibgaya villages with more than 15,000 houses fled, leaving behind all their property and the state. All this wealth is now left to Armenians, the looted property is worth several millions or even billions" [6, 135]. The information published in this newspaper is once again a proof that Armenians have taken possession of someone else's land by force and committed genocide, displacing the local population. Also, if you pay attention to the etymology of the listed village names, it shows that each of them belongs to Azerbaijan. However, later Armenians changed the names of the native lands of Azerbaijan in order to Armenianize them by implementing a genocidal policy against toponyms. With this, they are trying to deny that these territories historically belong to Azerbaijan and falsify history. However, the names

mentioned in sources and historical documents and their origin also expose Armenian lies.

There is also information about the subsequent resettlement of Armenians to these areas in English documents kept in the archives of Great Britain. Of these, the memorandum prepared by the political intelligence department of the British Foreign Ministry on October 28, 1918 states: "When solving the Armenian question, it should be taken into account that its center of gravity is not in the Caucasus, but in the south of Asia Minor. Armenians came to the Caucasus from Turkey mainly as refugees during the last decades during the Russian rule. The Russian government used them here to incite disputes between Georgians and Tatars" [2, 110]. Important facts related to the genocides committed by Armenians in Azerbaijan were also reflected in the documents of the British government stored in the British archives. Among them, the letters sent by the high commissioner for the South Caucasus appointed by the British government, General O. Wardrop, to his government, the information contained in his correspondence can be cited as an example. In his report sent to London on October 2, 1919, he informed: "Recently, the Armenians destroyed 60 Muslim villages in Yeni Beyazid, Alexandropol and Iravan regions" [5, 30].

In the letters sent by O. Wardrop in December 1919, it was mentioned that the Armenians killed the civilian population - the Muslim population, including women and children, in the mosque, and the Muslims of Zangezur are in a state of panic. It should be noted that in addition to O. Wardrop's information, the Azerbaijani government also sent a letter to the British Prime Minister Lord Curzon, informed about the genocide committed by the Armenians in Zangezur, and the British government officially recognized these territories as Azerbaijani territory. [5, 31].

It is known from the British documents that the British government tried to use the Armenians against the Ottomans, and even for this purpose Andranik was provided with weapons and financial support for the resistance against the Turks. Genocides committed by Armenians in Azerbaijan were evaluated as damage to British plans. In this regard, it is stated in official documents and correspondence that if the Armenians do not stop the massacres, the aid to them will be stopped. O. Wardrop wrote about this in document No. 52 sent on January 28, 1920: "The main purpose of my visit to Yerevan was to put pressure on the Armenian Prime Minister to withdraw the regular troops from Zangezur and punish the culprits. I have already sent a telegram to his relatives that if the Armenian government does not stop the aggression, I will advise His Majesty's government not to help them" [5, 34] Each of these facts confirms that Armenians committed genocide against the people of Azerbaijan. In matters related to the genocide, it is once again proven that the events were committed by the political line of the Armenians and the state of Ararat.

The genocides carried out by Armenians in the territory of Iravan governorate in 1918-1920 were also reflected in the Ottoman archival documents. In these documents, it was also mentioned that he asked for help

from the Ottoman 15th regular army command to defend against Armenian oppression and atrocities committed by Armenians against the population. Among the documents of this period, there are also maps describing the territories where the Armenians committed genocide, which are historical sources of great importance in terms of specifying the territory covered by the massacres. One such map was drawn on July 3, 1919. The map called "Description of the places where Armenians committed atrocities against the population of Goyja" shows the areas where the Armenians committed genocide - Agbulag, Shoreyel, Gamarli and other areas. Another map drawn up in the same month shows regions affected by genocide such as Iravan, Big Vedi, Karalar, Shirazli, Khalisa, Sadarak, Alisar [11, 43].

In Ottoman archival documents from 1920, it is possible to find information about atrocities committed by Armenians, killing the population in an inhuman manner. An example of this is the documents where 50 children and teenagers were chopped with axes by Armenians in 1920 in Gizilkilsa village of Yerevan, their eyes were removed with red skewers, and people were burned in cauldrons and destroyed by torture. The documents belonging to the Ottoman archives once again prove that in 1918-1920, Armenians committed genocide against Azerbaijanis, invaded Azerbaijani territories by committing brutal murders, and as a result of all this, created a state for themselves in the historical lands of Azerbaijan.

The result

The territory of Western Azerbaijan, which is now the territory of the state called Armenia, is the historical land of Azerbaijan. There are historical sources, toponyms, and monuments that prove this place belongs to Turkish culture. However, Armenians living with the dreams of "Great Armenia" displaced the aboriginal population of this place from their native lands through genocide and deportation. When we look at history, we see that the current historical and political conditions are effective for Armenians in this regard. During Tsarist Russia and later during the USSR, Armenians used the opportunity for their own plans. The genocides carried out by the Armenians in 1918-1920 were a continuation of the massacres committed in 1905-1906 and the same policy they pursued. However, the policy of genocide and ethnic cleansing against Azerbaijan and Azerbaijanis did not end there. V. I. In December 1920, Zangezur was given to Armenia unconditionally as a result of the new colonial policy implemented in this region by the dictates of the Armenian and Georgian Bolsheviks, who had great influence in the ruling circles of Soviet Russia headed by Lenin. Armenians, who felt that this issue was completely resolved for their own benefit, did not object to the return of the Azerbaijani population expelled from Zangezur to their homes in order to create temporary calm, but in the following years, they again displaced the Azerbaijanis from their native places. Azerbaijanis were deported from the Armenian SSR from 1948-53 by the hands of the Soviet regime. Armenians were settled in their houses, native and historical territories. The Armenians used all the means and every opportunity to expel the Azerbaijanis

from this area. Starting from the late 1980s, they managed to completely expel Azerbaijanis from Western Azerbaijan using the current political situation in the USSR. These facts once again prove that the actions of Armenians are against humanity and international law norms. The rights of the displaced Azerbaijani population must be restored. This is the historical and legal right of the expelled population.

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